

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) Profile in Bacterial Isolates from Street Food

Miguel Alfonso Ruíz-Rosas

Faculty of Biological Sciences, Benemérita Autonomous University of Puebla, Mexico

Rocío Pérez-y-Terrón

*Laboratory 127 of Microbiology, Molecular Biology and Biomaterials,
BIO 1 Building, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Benemérita Autonomous University of Puebla, Mexico*

Abstract

In the present study, a total of 14 bacterial isolates were obtained from food stalls on public roads in the City of Puebla, Mexico; these bacteria can cause serious infections in public health. Antimicrobial susceptibility was evaluated with 12 different antibiotics. The purpose of the project was to determine the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of antibiotics for isolates exhibiting antimicrobial susceptibility using an adapted E-test technique. The main genera found in the samples were *Escherichia*, *Klebsiella*, *Salmonella*, and *Pseudomonas*, with *Klebsiella* being the most prevalent. Cephalothin exhibited the highest inhibition rate against the isolates, with an MIC of 2 µg/mL, indicating that a high dose is required to achieve adequate inhibition. This provides information on clinically relevant antibiotic resistance and on the agents responsible for significant gastrointestinal infections.

Keywords: *Foodborne illnesses, resistance, minimum inhibitory concentration.*

Suggested citation: Ruíz-Rosas, M.A., & Pérez-y-Terrón, R. (2026). Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) Profile in Bacterial Isolates from Street Food. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 3(1), 153-158. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2026.3(1).15

Introduction

Foodborne illnesses (FBIs) are caused by consuming food or water contaminated by microorganisms, with bacteria being the most common agents (Delgado, 2018). Symptoms include nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal pain, fever, and sometimes neurological problems or death (Fernández et al., 2021). For this reason, FBIs are the leading cause of death worldwide, considered the most widespread public health problem globally (Murillo et al., 2019). The prevalence of bacteria in food depends on several factors, including temperature, storage conditions, pH, and water availability (Soto et al., 2016). An antibiotic is typically defined as a naturally occurring or synthetically produced substance that inhibits or eliminates bacteria (Pérez, 2021). Some bacteria can develop antibiotic resistance; this occurs when bacteria develop mechanisms to evade the effects of these medications, making infections more difficult to treat and increasing the risk of serious complications or even death (Oteo, 2019). Therefore, the main objective of this study is to determine the MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration) of antibiotics using the E-test technique in bacteria from food.

Materials and Methods

The samples were collected from 10 different street taco stands in downtown Puebla. Inclusion criteria for food ingredients were set to obtain uniform samples. The samples were then taken to the laboratory for analysis. They were inoculated onto three different media: bismuth sulfide agar, brilliant green agar, and Salmonella-Shigella agar, which are selective and differential media used to isolate food samples. The cultures were incubated at 37°C in a Witeg IF-150 incubator for isolation.

To identify the strains, macroscopic and microscopic morphological tests were performed, along with biochemical tests for citrate, lysine, iron, triple sugar (TSI), motility, indole, ornithine (MIO), and urea. Once identified, a plate count was performed to determine the standard dose (CFU/mL), which was used in antibiotic susceptibility testing according to the method proposed by Muñoz et al. in 2016. To determine antibiotic susceptibility, antibiograms were performed on each strain at a dose of 1×10^6 CFU/mL using commercial PT-35 ID MULTIBAC I.D. multidiscs containing the following antibiotics: amikacin, ampicillin, cephalothin, cefotaxime, ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, nitrofurantoin, carbenicillin, gentamicin, netilmicin, norfloxacin, and sulfamethoxazole-trimethoprim. After incubation, the inhibition zones were measured with calipers to determine whether the strain was resistant or susceptible to the antibiotic, based on the zone diameter and the specific antibiotic. Only bacteria that tested susceptible were further analyzed.

The Epsilon test is a laboratory method used to determine a microorganism's antimicrobial susceptibility to a specific antibiotic, providing a straightforward and precise means of measuring the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), the lowest concentration of an antimicrobial capable of inhibiting the growth of a microorganism (Jaramillo, 1998). It employs a strip with an antibiotic concentration gradient, and an inhibition ellipse is observed around the strip (Figure 1). For this purpose, a modified E-test technique proposed by Contreras et al. (2020) was used, which required preparing 1:10 dilutions of each antibiotic. It should be noted that most antibiotics include specific instructions for preparing the diluent and the lyophilized antibiotic; therefore, this was not addressed. Filter paper sensitizing discs, 6 mm in diameter with 5-micron pores, were used. Once the dilutions were prepared, 6 μ L of each dilution were added to the corresponding sensitizing disc and dried to maximize absorption. Mass plating was performed with 30 μ L of culture at 1×10^{-6} CFU/mL in 20 cm diameter Petri dishes. The highest concentration disc was placed at the edge of the Petri dish, and the remaining dilutions were arranged in a straight line toward the center (Figure 1). To determine the MIC, the lowest dilution that showed an inhibitory effect was identified. For example, if an antibiotic with a 250 mg/mL solution showed an inhibitory effect at dilution 4, the original solution was divided by 10,000, and so on, according to the lowest dilution at which inhibition was observed, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Modified Epsilon Test (E-test modified)

$$\text{CMI} = \text{Original solution} / 10^X$$

X=Number of the last dilution in which the growth-inhibiting effect occurs

Figure 2. Formula to Obtain the CMI Value

Results

Fourteen isolates were collected from ten different sites. These isolates were found in only 7 out of the 10 public establishments. Based on the identification methods used, the genera identified included Escherichia, Salmonella, Klebsiella, and Pseudomonas. Klebsiella was the most common, accounting for 5 of the 14 isolates, while Salmonella was only 2. Antibiotic susceptibility data are provided in Table 1. To assess whether an antibiotic was effective, the guide included with the commercial multidisc was consulted. The results of the E-test are shown in Table 2; the MIC was calculated using the provided formula, and the concentration at which the antibiotic inhibited bacterial growth was observed (Figure 3).

Table 1. Results of Antibiotic Susceptibility

Gender	Bacterial Isolates	CF	CFX	CA	CPL	AM	CL	NF	NT	GE	ST	NOF	AK
Escherichia	T2-A	S	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	R
Klebsiella	T3-A	S	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
Klebsiella	T3-B	S	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Escherichia	T3-D	S	S	R	R	R	S	S	R	R	R	R	R
Pseudomonas	T3-F	R	S	R	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
Pseudomonas	T5-A	S	R	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
Klebsiella	T6-A	S	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S
Klebsiella	T7-A	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	S
Escherichia	T7-B	R	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	S	R	R	S
Pseudomonas	T7-C	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	S
Salmonella	T8-B	S	S	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R
Escherichia	T9-A	R	R	R	R	R	S	S	R	S	R	R	S
Salmonella	T9-C	S	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	S	R	R	R
Klebsiella	T9-E	R	S	R	S	R	R	R	R	R	R	R	R

Note: *Cephalothin (CF), Cefotaxime (CFX), Carbenicillin (CA), Ciprofloxacin (CPL), Ampicillin (AM), Chloramphenicol (CL), Nitrofurantoin (NF), Netilmicin (NT), Gentamicin (GE), Sulfamethoxazole-Trimethoprim (ST), Norfloxacin (NOF), Amikacin (AK); **Resistant (R), Sensitive (S)

Table 2. MIC of the Isolates that Showed Susceptibility

Bacterial Isolates	Gender	Antibiotic	MIC
T7-C	Pseudomonas	AK	0.025 µg/ml
		GE	0.4 µg/ml
T3-F	Pseudomonas	CFX	0.0000025 µg/ml
		CL	0.005 µg/ml

T3-B	Klebsiella	CF	0.2 µg/ml
		CPL	0.0083 µg/ml
		CFX	0.00025 µg/ml
T7-A	Klebsiella	CPL	0.00083 µg/ml
		NFX	0.006 µg/ml
		AK	0.025 µg/ml
T6-A	Klebsiella	AK	0.25 µg/ml
		GE	0.004 µg/ml
T9-E	Klebsiella	CPL	0.00000083 µg/ml
T5-A	Pseudomonas	CPL	0.083 µg/ml
		CF	0.2 µg/ml
T3-A	Klebsiella	CF	0.0000002 µg/ml
		CFX	0.0000025 µg/ml
		CPL	0.000083 µg/ml
		CL	0.005 µg/ml
T3-D	Escherichia	CFX	0.00025 µg/ml
		CF	2 µg/ml
		CL	0.000005 µg/ml
		NFX	0.0016 µg/ml
T9-A	Escherichia	AK	0.25 µg/ml
		GE	0.04 µg/ml
		CL	0.0005 µg/ml
		NFX	0.006 µg/ml
T7-B	Escherichia	AK	0.025 µg/ml
		CL	0.5 µg/ml
		CFX	0.25 µg/ml
		CPL	0.000083 µg/ml
		GE	0.04 µg/ml
T2-A	Escherichia	CL	0.000005 µg/ml
		CPL	0.00000083 µg/ml
		GE	0.0084 µg/ml
		CF	0.00002 µg/ml
		CFX	0.000025 µg/ml
T8-B	Salmonella	CFX	0.00025 µg/ml
		CPL	0.0000000083 µg/ml
		CL	0.0000000005 µg/ml
		CF	0.02 µg/ml
T9-C	Salmonella	GE	0.04 µg/ml
		CPL	0.000083 µg/ml
		CFX	0.00025 µg/ml
		CF	0.02 µg/ml
		CL	0.005 µg/ml

Note:*Cephalothin (CF), Cefotaxime (CFX), Ciprofloxacin (CPL), Chloramphenicol (CL), Nitrofurantoin (NF), Gentamicin (GE), Norfloxacin (NOF), Amikacin (AK)

Determination of MIC using a modified E-test technique, where the highest value was 0.04 µg/ml of the antibiotic gentamicin.

Discussion

The presence of bacteria that cause gastrointestinal infections in street food, along with the illnesses they cause, can pose a public health problem for locals and visitors alike. However, the presence of pathogenic bacteria can depend on the time of year the sampling takes place, as temperature significantly influences

their growth. Similarly, bacterial diversity can vary by sample type; in this study, uniform samples were collected by taco type and ingredients. Additionally, antibiotic resistance may be related to the specific antibiotic used, since treating a gastrointestinal infection is not the same as treating a urinary tract infection caused by the same species. Therefore, the goal of this study is not to dispute existing theories but to demonstrate the presence of pathogenic bacteria in food and their response to antibiotics. Future research could explore different variables in sample collection and compare their effects.

Figure 3. Determination of MIC using E-test

Conclusion

Bacteriological analyses indicate that street food stalls pose a health risk to the community due to the presence of pathogenic bacteria in their products. The genus *Klebsiella* was the most frequently detected, followed by *Salmonella*. Cephalothin had the most significant inhibitory effect, with a MIC of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, while chloramphenicol had the least, with a MIC of 0.0000000005 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Contreras Cerón, R., Rivera Tapia, J. A., Morales Lara, L., & Pérez-y-Terrón, R. (2020). Determination of The Antimicrobial Sensitivity of Isolated Sea and Mangrove Bacteria in The State of Veracruz, Mexico, Using the Modified E-Test Technique. *Research In Medical & Engineering Sciences*.
- Delgado Gómez, A., Sandra Toledo, L., Bonfini Quintero, G., Higuera Donado, Y., Avila Roo, Y., & Valero Leal, K. (2018). Calidad microbiológica de ensaladas crudas que se expeden en puestos ambulantes de comida rápida de la ciudad de Maracaibo, Venezuela. *Kasmera*.
- Fernández, S., Marcía, J., Bu, J., Baca, Y., Chávez, V., Montoya, H., . . . Ore, F. (2021). Enfermedades transmitidas por alimentos (ETAs): una alerta para el consumidor. *Ciencia Latina Revista Científica Multidisciplinar*, 5(2), 2284–2298. https://doi.org/10.37811/cl_rcm.v5i2.433
- Jaramillo Velásquez, S. (Enero-Junio de 1998). Prueba Épsilon (E-test). *CES MEDICINA*, 12(1), 34–41.

Muñoz Rojas, J., Morales García, Y. E., Báez Rogelio, A., Quintero Hernández, V., Rivera Urbalejo, A. P., & Pérez-y-Terrón, R. (2016). Métodos económicos para la cuantificación de microorganismos. *Science Associated Editors L.L.C.*

Murillo Zavala, A., Marcillo Carvajal, C., Peñaherrera Ortiz, M., & Pinales Pincay, I. G. (Septiembre de 2019). Síndrome diarreico infeccioso causado por Salmonella spp. *Revista Científica Mundo de la Investigación y el Conocimiento*, 3(3), 493–508. <http://recimundo.com/index.php/es/article/view/533>

Oteo Iglesias, J. (2019). Comprendiendo la resistencia a los antibióticos. *RIECS*, 84–89.

Pérez Gracia, M. T. (2021). *La pandemia silenciosa: resistencia bacteriana a los antibióticos*. Madrid: CEU Ediciones.

Soto Varela, Z., Pérez Lavalle, L., & Estrada Alvarado, D. (Enero-Abril de 2016). Bacteria causing foodborne diseases: an overview in Colombia. *Salud Uninorte*, 32(1), 105–122. <https://doi.org/10.14482/sun.32.1.8598>

